

CHIZIQLI TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI

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Annotatsiya. Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini sonli yechish amaliy matematikaning muhim masalalaridan biridir. Fizika, mexanika, texnika va umuman tabiatshunoslikning xilma-xil masalalari algebraik tenglamalar tizimini yechishga olib keldi. Masalan, mexanik sistemaning tebranish chastotalarining kvadratlari matritsalarini xarakteristik tenglamalarining ildizlari bo'ladi, bunday tenglamalar esa n -darajali algebraik tenglamalardir.

Kalit so'zlar. Aniqmas sistema, aniq sistema, hamjoyli bo'lmagan, hamjoyli, koeffitsient, xarakteristik tenglama, matritsa, amaliy matematika.

Barcha noma'lumlarning darajasi birdan katta bo'lmagan tenglamalar "chiziqli tenglama" deyiladi:

$$a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n = b \quad (1)$$

Tenglamani to'g'ri sonli tenglikka aylantiruvchi $x = (\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n)$, $\varepsilon_i \in F$, $i=\overline{1, n}$ vektor berilgan tenglamaning yechimi deyiladi.

Agar $b=0$ bo'lsa, (1) tenglama **bir jinsli** deyiladi. Bir xil noma'lumli chiziqli tenglamalardan iborat bir nechta tenglamalarni birga yechish, ya'ni chiziqli tenglamalarni yechish masalasi ko'p uchraydi.

Birga ko'rilayotgan bir xil noma'lumli bir nechta chiziqli tenglamalar to'plami "**chiziqli tenglamalar**" tizimi deyiladi.

Umumiy ko'rinishda olingan chiziqli tenglamalar tizimida odatda koeffitsientlar va ozod hadlar ko'p bo'lgani va shunga ko'ra ularni turli harflar bilan belgilash uchun alifbodagi harflar yetishmagani sababli koeffitsientlarni va ozod hadlarni quyidagicha belgilash usuli islatiladi:

Berilgan ikkita chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi uchun birinchisining har bir yechimi ikkinchi uchun ham yechim bo'lsa, ikkinchi chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi birinchi chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasining natijasi deyiladi.

Ikkita chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi teng kuchli deyiladi, agar birinchisining har bir yechimi ikkinchisiga yechim bo'lsa va aksincha.

Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasining noma'lumlari oldidagi koeffitsientlardan tuzilgan (**A**) **matritsa asosiy matritsasi**, noma'lumlar oldidagi koeffitsiyentlar va ozod hadlardan iborat (**B**) **matritsa kengaytirilgan matritsa** deyiladi.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} & b_2 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} & b_n \end{pmatrix}$$

Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechish masalasi bu sistemaning koeffitsientlaridan tuzilgan A to'g'ri to'rtburchak jadvalning xossalariga bog'liq. Bunday jadval s satrli n ta ustunli matritsa ($s \times n$ matritsa) deyiladi, (a_{ij}) yoki $\|a_{ij}\|$ ko'rinishida yozish mumkin. Bu A matritsada a_{ij} sonlar matritsaning elementlari deyiladi. Barcha $s \times n$ - matritsalar to'plamini $M_{s,n}$ orqali belgilaymiz.

A matritsaning har bir satriga R ustida n -o'lchamli vektor deb qarash mumkin. Uning i -satrini $(a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{in})$ ko'rinishida yozamiz. Keyinchalik esa A matritsaning satrlarini mos ravishda A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n orqali kiritamiz. A matritsaning ustunlariga R ustida s -o'lchamli vektor deb qarash mumkin. Uning j -ustunini ushbu

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{1j} \\ a_{2j} \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ a_{ij} \end{pmatrix}$$

belgini $[a_{1j}, a_{2j}, \dots, a_{ij}]$ bilan almashtiramiz. Keyinchalik A matritsaning ustunlarini mos ravishda A^1, A^2, \dots, A^n kabi belgilaymiz.

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